

Influence of Artificial Intelligence Tools on Teaching and Learning Outcomes in Public Secondary Schools in Plateau State: Opportunities and Challenges

Roseline W. Walu,¹ Lawal Usman,² Haruna Abdullahi,³
Jummai Lucas Hamidu⁴

¹*Dept. of Educational Foundations, University of Jos, (walu@unijos.edu.ng) 08069177257*

²*Tafawa Balewa College of Education, Kangare, School of Arts and Social Sciences, Social Studies Department, (lawalusmantilde@gmail.com) 08039316468*

³*Umar Suleiman College of Education, Gashu, Yobe State, (harunaabdullahi3771@gmail.com)*

⁴*Federal Government College Jos, Plateau State, (jummailucas@gmail.com)*

The study examined the influence of artificial intelligence tools on teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Plateau State. While AI holds significant potential for effective lesson delivery, certain concerns were raised about its excessive overreliance on automated systems and the possible erosion of students' critical thinking skills. 5 research objectives and research questions were raised in this study. 2 instruments were developed, STALOSN and SIAATLS for administrators, teachers and students respectively. The instruments went through validation by experts and a reliability test using Cronbach Alpha method with a reliability index of 0.72. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics. Results of findings revealed a low level of awareness and preparedness for the use of AI tools for teaching and learning in public secondary schools in Plateau State. Also revealed were challenges in the adoption of AI technology with sociological implications for equity in its implementation across urban and rural schools and between the privilege and the underprivileged socio-economic classes.

Keywords:
Artificial
Intelligence,
Secondary Education
Pedagogy.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as one of the most transformative technologies in the 21st century, with significant implications for the educational sector worldwide. AI can be broadly defined as the capability of computer systems to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as problem solving, speech recognition, decision making, and learning from experience (Russell & Norvig, 2021). In the educational domain, AI tools are increasingly deployed to facilitate adaptive learning, automate administrative tasks,

provide real-time feedback, and personalize learning pathways (Luckin et al., 2016).

Globally, the adoption of AI in education has been driven by the need to improve learning efficiency, to cater to diverse learner needs, and prepare students for a technology-driven economy (Holmes et al., 2019). In primary and secondary school settings, AI tools, such as intelligent tutoring systems, learning analytics platforms, and automated grading software are helping teachers identify students' strengths and weaknesses, thereby enabling targeted interventions (Baker & Smith, 2019). These applications are not

limited to developed nations; emerging economies are also integrate AI solutions to bridge the gaps in educational access and quality (UNESCO, 2021).

In Nigeria, the conversation around AI in education is gaining momentum due to the growing penetration of mobile technology, improved Internet connectivity in urban areas, and the emergence of EdTech platforms such as Afrilearn, uLesson, and Digilearn. These platforms employ AI-driven algorithms to customize learning materials according to student performance, thereby addressing individual learning needs (Okonkwo, 2022). However, the Nigerian educational landscape faces systemic challenges—such as inadequate infrastructure, digital illiteracy among teachers, and unequal access between urban and rural schools—that affect the equitable adoption of AI tools (Ogunleye & Adeyemi, 2023).

The potential benefits of AI tools in Nigerian primary and secondary education are multifaceted, including enhanced learning engagement, improved assessment accuracy, support for inclusive education (particularly for students with disabilities), and more efficient resource allocation (World Bank, 2020). For instance, speech recognition AI can assist learners with reading difficulties, while predictive analytics can help educators identify at-risk students early, thus enabling timely interventions (Luckin et al., 2016). Furthermore, AI can help alleviate the burden of teacher shortages by automating routine instructional and administrative tasks, allowing educators to focus on more complex pedagogical responsibilities (Baker & Smith, 2019).

Despite these advantages, the integration of AI into secondary education has raised important concerns. One of the most pressing is the digital divide, where students in under-resourced schools are risk being excluded from AI-enabled

learning opportunities due to lack of internet access, insufficient hardware, or inadequate electricity supply (Afolabi, 2021). Additionally, ethical issues—such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the potential dehumanization of teaching—pose challenges that must be addressed through robust policies and teacher training (UNESCO, 2021). Overreliance on AI could also lead to a diminished role for teachers in shaping students' socio-emotional skills, which remain critical for holistic development (Holmes et al., 2019).

This challenge is even more pronounced in Plateau State, a State that is historically classified as one of the educationally backward states. The public secondary schools in Plateau cater for majority of school aged children which form this diverse population, from both rural and urban settlements with more children from low-income families.

From a sociological perspective, AI in education is both a democratizing force and a potential agent of inequality. While it can expand access to high-quality learning resources across geographical boundaries, its benefits may disproportionately favor those with better digital infrastructure, thereby widening educational disparities. In the Nigerian context, where public primary and secondary schools often lack basic ICT resources, the risk of excluding large segments of the student population from AI-enhanced learning is significant (Ogunleye & Adeyemi, 2023).

Considering these realities, understanding the opportunities and challenges of AI integration in education requires a balanced and context-sensitive approach. Therefore, this theoretical paper examines the influence of artificial intelligence tools on teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary public schools of Plateau state.

Statement of the Problem

The introduction of AI in public secondary education in Plateau state has the potential to revolutionize teaching and learning as it can enable personalized instruction, provide timely feedback, and diagnose difficulties. However, their integration into classrooms is not problem-free. In many secondary schools in Plateau state access to reliable Internet, electricity, and functional devices remains a significance barrier. The enthusiasm for AI often overshadows the reality that technology can unintentionally marginalize learners from low-income or rural backgrounds. Moreover, the use of AI education raises issues of teacher preparedness, over-reliance on automated systems, and the possible erosion of critical thinking skills among students.

Without deliberate frameworks for equitable access, ethical data management, and professional teacher development, AI tools could exacerbate rather than bridge the educational divide. The problem, therefore, is not merely whether AI tools should be adopted, but how they can be integrated into secondary education in ways that maximize benefits while minimizing harm.

System marked by infrastructural deficits, unequal access, insufficient teacher capacity, and ethical concerns – pose significant barriers to its effective adoption. This raises the following critical issues:

How can AI tools can be implemented in ways that address, rather than deepen, educational inequalities, the framework that guides the equitable and context-sensitive integration of AI in secondary schools, and how Nigerian teachers can be empowered to effectively harness AI while retaining the human elements of teaching?

Aim/Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the influence of artificial intelligent tools on teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Plateau State. The specific objectives of the study are:

- To investigate the extent of principals, teachers' and student's awareness of the adoption of AI tools in teaching and learning
- To investigate the extent of readiness of public secondary schools for the usage of AI tools for teaching and learning
- To find out perceived advantages of adopting AI tools in public secondary schools in Plateau state.
- To find out perceived disadvantages of adopting AI tools in public secondary schools in Plateau state
- To investigate perceived challenges in the adoption of AI tools in public secondary schools in Plateau state

Research Questions

- To what extent are principals, teachers and students of public secondary schools aware of the adoption of AI tools in teaching and learning?
- To extent are public secondary schools in Plateau state ready for the usage of AI tools in teaching and learning?
- What are the perceived advantages of adopting AI tools in public secondary schools in Plateau state?
- What are the perceived advantages of adopting AI tools in public secondary schools in Plateau state?
- What are the perceived challenges in the adoption of AI tools in public secondary schools in plateau state?

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in two complementary sociological perspectives that provide an analytical lens for understanding the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in primary and secondary education: Structural Functionalism and Conflict Theory. While structural functionalism focuses on the advantages of AI tools, structural conflict theory emphasizes the disadvantages and challenges of these tools in primary and secondary education.

Structural Functionalism

Structural functionalism, as advanced by Émile Durkheim (1912) and later refined by Talcott Parsons (1951), views society as a complex system comprising interdependent parts working together to promote stability and social order. Education, from this perspective, serves as a critical institution that socializes individuals, transmits culture, and equips members with the skills necessary for societal participation (Haralambos & Holborn, 2017).

AI tools, in this framework, can be seen as innovations designed to enhance the functions of the education system. For example, AI-enabled personalized learning aligns with the functionalist goal of optimizing human capital by tailoring instruction to meet diverse learner needs (Holmes et al., 2019). Automated grading and performance analytics can support the system's efficiency by reducing administrative burdens and allowing educators to focus on higher-order teaching tasks.

However, functionalists also recognize that rapid technological changes require adaptation across the systems. In many public

secondary schools in Nigeria and Plateau in particular, teachers have large classes with sometimes over 80 students per class. All learning apps like eu lesson or Emodo can support the teacher's effort if students have access to these tools and this can promote practical exercises and feedback skills that are essential to development of Maths, English and Sciences. By aligning with the perspective of structural foundationalism, these are innovations that function towards effective teaching and learning. Thus from this perspective, social order is maintained which according to persons (1951) makes a society stable and cohesive.

Conflict Theory

Conflict theory, rooted in the work of Karl Marx (1867) and later expanded by Wright Mills (1959) and Randall Collins (1971), offers a contrasting perspective by emphasizing power relations, inequality, and competition over scarce resources. From this viewpoint, education is not merely a neutral mechanism for skill development but also a site where social inequalities are reproduced (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1977).

Applied to AI in education, conflict theory highlights the risk that these technologies could exacerbate existing disparities. Schools in affluent urban areas are more likely to have the infrastructure, funding, and trained staff needed to deploy AI effectively, whereas rural and low-income schools may lag behind, perpetuating unequal educational outcomes (Afolabi, 2021). Furthermore, corporate interests in AI development may prioritize profit over the equitable distribution of benefits, creating a dependency on proprietary platforms that limit local innovation and autonomy (Selwyn, 2019).

Conflict theorists have also drawn attention to cultural biases embedded in AI systems. When algorithms are trained predominantly on datasets from Western contexts, the resulting tools may fail to reflect the linguistic, cultural, and socioeconomic realities of Nigerian students, thereby marginalizing local knowledge systems (Russell & Norvig, 2021). This reinforces the notion that AI integration is not just a technological issue, but also a deeply sociological one involving question of equity, representation, and control.

This therefore implies that the elite and wealthy class families can support their children by access to AI equipped schools and this provides a head start in technologically driven areas whereas children in public schools without access to AI facilities will perpetually remain in low status jobs producing an underprivilege class.

Literature Review

The literature review examines existing scholarship on AI tools in education, with an emphasis on their advantages, disadvantages, and the Nigerian context.

Conceptualizing AI in Education

Artificial Intelligence in education (AIED) refers to the application of machine learning, natural language processing, and other AI techniques to enhance teaching, learning, and administrative processes (Luckin et al., 2016). Globally, AI tools such as adaptive learning platforms, intelligent tutoring systems, automated grading software, and predictive analytics have been increasingly adopted in both developed and developing contexts (Holmes et al., 2019).

Recent Development on Ai

In developed countries like the United States of America, China and United Kingdom, AI

has moved from the level of experimentation to the level of operational use in supporting personalization, automated feedback, curriculum diagnostics including formative feedback analyses (Carnegie learning 2025; UNESCO, 2025). China has launched a large scale AI-powered education experiments to track students' progress on time and provide a tailored feedback. Similarly the United State schools and universities are leveraging AI to enhance efficiency in lesson delivery and students engagement (Carnegie Learning, 2025).

Development on AI in advanced countries are supported by strong national commitments by robust infrastructure and internet connectivity like matured private public Ed-Teck ecosystems.

In contrast to developed countries particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. Progress towards AI is slow due to infrastructural constraints (UNESCO, 2023). While there is a growing awareness of AI tools and potential benefits, infrastructural challenges such as inadequate internet connectivity has slowed down the pace of implementation (UNESCO 2021). Nigeria is said to lag significantly behind advanced economies in education due to digital divides and policy limitations (African Centre for Technology Studies, 2023). From the literature, there is a sharp contrast in rates of advancement of AI technology and supportive government policies. The federal government of Nigeria made efforts to release funds to universities and colleges, yet progress remain slow (Omede and Omede, 2023). While Nigeria and similar developing countries are still navigating basic readiness issues like access, training and affordability, advanced countries are already at topmost level in integrating AI into their education systems. This

comparative gap presents an urgent need for Nigeria to evolve targeted policies and make investments to prepare Nigerian schools and particularly disadvantaged states like Plateau to harness AI's potential for improving teaching and learning outcomes.

Advantages of AI Tools in Education

Several studies have highlighted the transformative potential in education. First, AI enables personalized learning, adapting content and pacing to the individual needs of learners (Baker & Smith, 2019). Second, it offers real-time feedback, allowing students to promptly identify and address knowledge gaps promptly (Luckin et al., 2016). Third, AI can reduce administrative workloads by automating routine tasks, freeing teachers to focus on higher-level instructional design and mentorship (Holmes et al., 2019).

Moreover, AI can serve as a diagnostic tool to identify students at risk of underperformance and recommending targeted interventions (Russell & Norvig, 2021). In contexts where teacher shortages are acute-like such as in many Nigerian rural schools, AI tools can supplement instruction and extend learning opportunities beyond the traditional classroom.

Disadvantages and Risks of AI In Education

Despite these benefits, literature warns of several risks. The digital divide remains a major barrier, unequal access to Internet connectivity, devices, and electricity hinders the equitable implementation of AI in Nigerian schools (Ogunleye & Adeyemi, 2023). Teacher preparedness is another challenge many educators lack the training to integrate AI effectively into their pedagogical practices (UNESCO, 2021).

The ethical issues were also prominent. Data privacy concerns arise from the collection and storage of sensitive student information, often with inadequate legal safeguards (Selwyn, 2019). Algorithmic bias can perpetuate social and cultural inequalities, disadvantaging students whose linguistic or socio-cultural backgrounds are underrepresented in AI datasets (Russell & Norvig, 2021).

From a pedagogical standpoint, over-reliance on AI risks deskilling teachers and undermining the development of critical thinking, creativity, and interpersonal skills among students (Holmes et al., 2019). These concerns are particularly significant in primary and secondary education, where socio-emotional development is as crucial as cognitive learning.

Nigerian Policy and Implementation Context

Nigeria's National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (2020–2030) acknowledges the role of emerging technologies in national development but provides limited direction for AI in basic education (Okonkwo, 2022). The absence of explicit AI guidelines leaves schools and state ministries without a coherent strategy for integration. Pilot projects remain fragmented and donor-driven, with minimal coordination or sustainability plans.

Recent initiatives by private EdTech companies, such as Afrilearn, demonstrate that localized AI solutions can be developed. However, without systemic support—including infrastructure investment, teacher training, and regulatory oversight—these efforts may remain isolated successes rather than catalysts for nationwide transformation (Afolabi, 2021).

Nigerian Context And Policy Implications

In Nigeria, AI adoption in basic education is still emerging, with most initiatives driven by private EdTech firms rather than coordinated government policy. Afrilearn, uLesson, and DigiLearns represent localized attempts to leverage AI-like systems for curriculum delivery (Okonkwo & Mba, 2023). However, these platforms often require stable internet and modern devices, making them inaccessible to many rural schools (Adamu & Bello, 2020).

The Federal Ministry of Education has acknowledged the role of digital technologies in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 4) but lacks a specific national AI strategy for education (Federal Ministry of Education, 2022). Without targeted investments in infrastructure, teacher training, and content localization, AI adoption may remain inequitable and fragmented.

Method and Procedures

Research Design

The study adopts a descriptive research design in order to analyse the current state of awareness, and readiness of public secondary schools in plateau state for the adoption of AI tools in teaching and learning. The perception of respondents covering the advantages, disadvantages and challenges in the use of AI tools will be unveiled. The design is suitable since it does not involve the manipulation of variables, rather perceptions and outcomes occur naturally.

Population and Sample

The target population of this study consists of the following,

1,150 public secondary schools (both junior and senior), 1150 principals, 35,000 teachers and 140,000 students (world Bank 2009)

Sample

Using mixed method research according to Creswell and Plano Clark (20218), a 3% of the various populations were obtained as samples, 35 public secondary schools across the three senatorial zones of plateau state, 35 principals, 1050 teachers and 4,200 students. This according to Cress-well and Plano Clark (2018), a methodological principles of mixed research method considers 3% of large populations like schools as statistically adequate for representation. Below is a table showing population and sample of the study.

Table 1
Population and Sample of Schools, Principals, Teachers and Students

Group Type	Population	Sample size
Public Secondary schools	1150	35
Principals	1150	35
Teacher	35,000	1050
Students	140,000	4,200

Sources: World Bank (2009), Federal Ministry of Education (2015), UBE (2020)

Sampling Techniques

To select sample schools, firstly a multistage sampling technique was used to classify the schools into senatorial zones which are the North, Central and Southern zones. Secondly, a stratified sampling method was used to categorize the schools into urban and rural schools. The third stage considered enrollment figures of small medium and large schools. This was to reflect the diversity of the school's exposure to ICT availability. The fourth and the final stage was the use of proportionate random sampling method to choose schools from each stratum. A sample of 35 schools were thus selected.

For the sampling of principals, each school automatically sampled included a principal. This selection method yielded 35 principals. Considering the size population including location, a stratified sample was used to select 1050 teachers. Also, through a stratified random selection, a total of 4,200 students representing junior and senior secondary students were selected. Gender was also considered in the selection. This was to encourage gender representation

Instruments for Data Collection

Two instruments were used for data collection

1. School Administrators and Teachers Survey on influence of artificial intelligence tools on teaching and learning outcomes in secondary schools in Nigeria: Opportunities and challenges (STATLOS)
2. Students Survey on Influence of Artificial Intelligence Tools on Teaching and learning outcomes in secondary schools in Nigeria: Opportunities and challenges (SIAATLSN)

STATLOS is a 20 item questionnaire designed to survey the level of awareness, readiness for AI tools for teaching and learning, including the advantages, disadvantages and challenges of adopting AI tools in secondary education .. SIAATLSN is a 16 item questionnaire to elicit responses from students on their awareness of AI tools in learning, perception on the advantages and disadvantages of AI tools in leaning and challenges associated with AI in learning. The responses were based on five Likert scale of “to a very low extent”, “low extent”, “moderate extent”, “high extent” and “very high extent”. This response is for research question one. Research question two and three were also scaled as “highly

disadvantaged”, “disadvantaged”, “moderately disadvantaged” and “mostly disadvantaged”. Research question five also had a similar Likert scale which were “Very high challenge”. “High challenge”, “Moderate challenge”, “Low challenge”, “Very low challenge”. A mean of 3.0 is the criterion mean.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments

The two instruments, STATLOS and SIAATLSN went through content and construct validity through experts in educational technology, sociology and educational measurement and evaluation specialist to ensure that the domains of digital readiness technological infrastructures and equity in the adoption of AI are well scrutinized for clarity and comprehensiveness. The final copy of the validated instruments was subjected to a test-retest reliability method. The result was correlated using the Cronbach Alpha method. A co-efficient of 0.72 was obtained which testified to the internal consistency and reliability of the instruments.

Method of Data Collection

Ethical approval was obtained from the institutions of the authors for conducting the survey questionnaires STATLOS, and SIAATLSN were administered to the schools through the permission of the principals with the help of research assistants and the authors in this study.

Method of Data Analysis

The data was analysed using descriptive statistic like simple percentages, mean and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question One: To what extent are principals, teachers and students of public secondary schools in plateau state aware of the adoption of AI tools in teaching and learning.

Table 2: AI Tools For Teaching and Learning Awareness In Secondary Schools

Awareness Items	Respondents	Frequency Yes	%	Frequency No	%	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Principals	35	62%		13 (38%)		2.6	1.0	Moderate extent
Teachers	1050	43%		598 (57%)		2.1	1.1	Low extent
Students	4,200	35%		2,730 (65%)		1.9	0.7	Low extent
Total		1,944 (37%)		3,341 (63%)		2.2	1.0	Low extent

Field study: 2025

Results indicated a low extent of awareness in the adoption of AI tools at the secondary schools (M. 2.2; SD 1.0). Among principals and teachers 62% and 43% awareness levels were recorded respectively. Student

responses to awareness were 35%. An overall percentage of 37 shows that the awareness for the adoption of AI tools for teaching and learning at secondary schools' level in plateau state is at a low extent.

Research Question Two: To what extent are schools in plateau state ready for the usage of AI tools in Secondary Schools for teaching and learning.?

Table 3: Readiness Of Secondary Schools for AI Learning

Readiness Items	Respondents	Frequency %Yes	Frequency %No	Mean	SD	Interpretation
ICT Labs	1085	412 (38%)	673 (62%)	2.0	0.9	Low readiness
Internet connection	1085	380 (35%)	705 (65%)	1.9	0.8	Low readiness
Teacher with ICT knowledge	1085	456 (42%)	629 (51%)	2.1	0.9	Low readiness
Administrative Support for Technology	1085	510 (47%)	575 (53%)	2.3	1.0	Moderate readiness
Total	1085	439 (40%)	646 (60%)	2.1	0.9	Low readiness

Field study: 2025

Results in table 3 indicates a low extent of readiness in secondary schools in adopting AI tools (M=2.1, SD=0.9). Responses across schools indicated a low-level of readiness for ICT laboratories with 38% response rate. Also low levels of readiness were observed for

internet connection (35%) and moderate level for teacher's with knowledge of ICT (42%). Also, administrative support for technology was moderately low (47%). An overall percentage score of 40% shows that there is a low extent of readiness for the adoption of AI in most schools.

Research Question 3: What are the perceived advantages of adopting AI tools in Secondary Schools in Plateau state?

Table 4: Perceived Advantages of AI Tools

Items	Respondents	Frequency %Yes	Frequency %No	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Improves and makes learning efficient	5285	3,648(69%)	1,637(31%)	3.5	1.1	High advantage
Provides individualized learning	5285	3,331(63%)	1,954(37%)	3.2	1.0	High advantage
Supports teachers' efforts in teaching	5285	3,543(67%)	1,742(33%)	3.4	1.1	High advantage
Improves school administration	5285	3,171(60%)	2,114(40%)	3.1	1.0	High advantage
Total	5285	3,423 (65%)	1,862 (35%)	3.3	1.1	High advantage

Field study: 2025

Table 4 shows that Respondents have agreed that AI improves and makes learning efficient (M3.1, SD=1.1) 69% respondents agreed that AI improves and makes learning efficient, 63% agreed that AI provides individualized learning. 67% agreed to

teachers' efforts being supplemented by AI tools while 60% believe that AI improves social administration. A total of 65% respondent have agreed o high advantages associated with the use of AI.

Research Question 4: What are the perceived disadvantages of AI tools in Secondary Schools in Plateau state?

Table 5: Perceived Disadvantages of AI Tools

Items	Respondents	Frequency %Yes	Frequency %No	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Less teacher interaction session	5285	3,543 (67%)	1,742 (33%)	3.4	1.1	High disadvantages
Reduces students intellectual	5285	3,647 (69%)	1,638 (31%)	3.5	1.0	High disadvantages
Equity gap between schools	5285	3,964 (75%)	1,321(25%)	3.8	1.1	High disadvantages
Equity gap among socio-economic groups	5285	4,070 (77%)	1,215(23%)	3.9	1.0	High disadvantages
Total	5285	3,806 (72%)	1,480(28%)	3.7	1.1	High disadvantages

Field study: 2025

Table 5 indicated that students perceive serious disadvantages of AI as teaching and learning tools (M=3.7, SD=1.1). They agreed that AI reduces the level of interaction between teachers and students (67%). They also agreed to low reduction in students' use of intellect to learn (69%). They foresee a dangerous trend in equity gap among schools

in the availability of I tools (75%) and an equity gap in the exposure of AI tools among students from different socioeconomic classes (77%). The overall percentage of 72% shows that majority of respondents have perceived a great disadvantage in the use of AI tools.

Research question 5: What are the perceived challenges of secondary schools in adopting AI tools for teaching and learning?

Table 6: Challenges in Adopting AI In Secondary Schools in Plateau State

Items	Respondents	Frequency %Yes	Frequency %No	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Lack of ICT infrastructure	5,285	4,175(79%)	1,110(21%)	4.0	1.0	Very high challenge
Lack of ICT training for Teachers	5,285	3,699(70%)	1,586(30%)	3.6	1.1	High challenge
Students' misuse of AI tools	5,285	3,699(70%)	1,586(30%)	3.6	1.0	High challenge
Inadequate Digital literacy among students	5,285	3,435(65%)	1,850(35%)	3.4	1.1	High challenge
High cost of devices and Internet facilities	5,285	3,964 (75%)	1,321(25%)	3.8	1.0	High challenge
Total	5,285	3,794 (72%)	1,491(28%)	3.7	1.1	High challenge

Field study: 2025

Table 5 reveals the challenges in the adoption of AI in Plateau State Public Secondary schools (M=3.7, S.D =1.1). They range from lack of ICT infrastructure (79%), which is the greatest, lack of training for teachers on ICT (70%), students misuse of AI tools (70%), inadequate digital literacy among students (65%) and high cost of devices and internet facilities (75%). The overall percentage of 72% responses proves that these challenges are highly significant.

Discussion of Results

The study investigated the influence of artificial intelligence tools on teaching and

learning outcomes in secondary schools in Plateau State, opportunities and challenges. The results have been presented according to five research questions. Research question one sought to investigate the extent to which principals, teachers and students are aware of the adoption of AI tools in teaching and learning. Percentage analysis revealed a lower extent of the level of awareness of principals, teachers and students on the adoption of AI tools for teaching and learning at secondary schools in Plateau State (37%). This is in line with findings by Okoye and

Adegboye 2022, who observed that in many schools, there are observed low technological awareness of AI tools for teaching and learning.

Research question two investigated the extent of readiness for the usage of AI tools for teaching and learning. Results analyzed in percentages show a low extent of readiness in the areas of ICT laboratories, internet connection, teacher ICT knowledge and administrative support for technology (40%). These findings support UNICEF (2021) on reports of low level of infrastructures to support digital education especially in disadvantaged areas in Nigeria. For research question three on the perceived advantages of AI tools in learning among students of secondary schools. Principals, teachers and students to a high extent perceived lesson delivery, individualized instructions, support to teachers in teaching and learning, improvement in school administration as advantages derived from the adoption of AI tools (65%). This finding is supported by Holmes et al (2019) that AI supports classroom teaching and learning efficiency.

Research question four focused on the perceived disadvantages of AI tools on teaching and learning. Respondents identified areas of high disadvantages in the adoption of AI tools. These areas are less teacher interaction with students, a limitation to students' intellectual capacity for academics, equity gap among schools in the acquisition of AI tools and equity gap in the knowledge of AI between children from privilege and underprivilege homes (72%). This raises a great sociological concern about AI as a potential agent of inequality as the high response shows that it benefits may favour mostly schools with better ICT and infrastructural facilities, mostly located in

urban areas. Underprivilege schools may face the risk of exclusion and this can widen educational gap. From the respondents, it is perceived that, children from low incomes class may face the risk of being denied the benefits of AI because by their low socioeconomic level, they are already disadvantaged as a segment of the population that cannot enjoy the benefits derived from AI learning. Research question 5 investigated the perceived challenges of secondary schools in adopting AI tools. The perceived challenges identified were, lack of ICT infrastructures, lack of ICT training for teachers, students misuse of AI tools, inadequate digital literacy among students and high cost of internet services (72%). These findings supports UNESCO (2023) reports on inadequate infrastructure and training as major challenges of AI education reforms in sub-Sahara Africa.

Conclusion

This study examined the influence of artificial intelligence tools on teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Plateau State. The findings revealed a low-level awareness of stakeholders in education like principals, teachers and students in AI driven technology in leaning. The findings also revealed the low readiness in public schools for AI for teaching and learning. Perceived advantages and disadvantaged including challenges of AI adoption in schools were also investigated. The study concludes that Plateau State as one of the disadvantage states in education is marked by infrastructural deficits, poor ICT and internet connectivity include low students and teachers' digital competence which limits AI adoption in public schools of Plateau State. The study ended with recommendations to advance the course of

AI implementation in secondary schools in Plateau State.

Recommendations

- Plateau state government in collaboration with federal government should make the provision of ICT infrastructures, internet connectivity and AI technological infrastructures a top priority.
- The government should conduct a large-scale literacy to train teachers and students on AI tools and adapt them to curriculum delivery.
- Both federal and state government should form a partnership with companies such as Nigerian EdTech Companies to adapt AI tools and use local languages for more effective delivery.
- Schools' administrators should be given all the support required to adopt AI at secondary school level.
- Given the significant number of students in rural areas, government should ensure the provision of AI tools and equip the rural schools for readiness of AI for teaching and learning.
- Sensitization awareness by schools should be carried out to parents and communities to enlighten them of the role of Ai in improving leaning outcomes.
- Plateau State Ministry of education should initiate pilot AI projects in selected school including the rural areas, monitor them and build models for wider adoption across the states.

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